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Abstract

The relationship between work-life balance and employee motivation in Jakarta's public sector is investigated in this article. The conceptual framework for exploring research variables is constructed using motivational theories and work-life balance theories. This is a descriptive study that employs a qualitative inductive approach. The total sample size for this study is 86 respondents who work in Jakarta's local government. A self-administered survey questionnaire was used to collect data. Personal life has a substantial impact on work, according to the findings. The majority of respondents choose flexible work arrangements and working from home. Females, on the other hand, are more ready to work from home than males. Furthermore, females, as opposed to males, are far more organised in balancing work commitments and personal life agendas, according to the data. Furthermore, rather than extra money or a bonus, all employees choose to take vacation. Finally, working longer hours is the most demotivating aspect of the job.

Keywords: Employee Motivation, Flexibility, Organizational Support, Work-Life balance

1. Introduction

1.1. Conceptual Outline

Work-Life Balance (WLB) is a broad notion that encompasses a healthy balance between work and aspiration on the one hand, and enjoyment, vacation, and family life on the other. Long working hours, as well as the strength and intensity of work, have continually risen to the top of workers' complaints. Work-life balance was first conceptualised in terms of work-family conflict, which was defined as the simultaneous occurrence of two or more sets of pressures such that compliance with one made compliance with the other more difficult (Kahn et al., 1964). The composition of the work and family life spheres has shifted dramatically throughout time. Working men and women today encounter a variety of obstacles on a daily basis, which can lead to a disconnect between their professional and personal lives. Work-family conflicts occur when one's participation in one role is incompatible with the other's participation in the other (Lobel, 1991). As a result, a lack of work-life balance affects a working individual's performance both at work and at home. Employees that have a better work-life balance are more likely to contribute to the organization's growth and success.

2. Review of Literature

Work-life balance is defined as a balance between work, family, and individual responsibility, in which each individual fulfils their obligations by balancing their personal and professional roles, as well as their responsibilities as a partner or parent (Shen, 2011; Chandra, 2012). Work-life balance is based on an employee's desire to strike a good balance between their desire to fully participate in work and feel comfortable while also giving their best effort to their loved ones (Bhalerao, 2013; Daipuria & Kakar, 2013; Lavoie, 2014; Kelliher et al., 2019). According to certain research, work-life balance has an indirect effect that helps employees enhance their well-being and develop good attitudes and life strategies (Zheng et al., 2016). Job-life balance is based on the premise that work and personal life should complement each other in order for one's life to be perfect. Two characteristics that help to create a good work-life balance are enjoyment of life and a desire to accomplish something (Bataineh, 2019). Organizations require productivity, and in order to achieve that, they seek for individuals who have a better work-life balance, as a person with a better work-life balance will contribute significantly to the organization's growth and success (Salolomo & Agbaeze, 2019).

Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2019) indicate that three main dimensions must be understood and examined in general when it comes to work-life balance. These dimensions are societal, organisational, and personal. As a result, the notion and circumstances surrounding an employee's work-life balance have varying meanings depending on the individual's attributes and perspectives.

Changing job opportunities and work-related stress necessitate a grasp of how to strike a work-life balance. (Hite & McDonald, 2020; Darwish et al., 2020). Maintaining a healthy balance between life and work will improve our mental well-being and help us stay motivated. Work-life balance influences individual motivation and personal life through indirectly encouraging and improving work motivation (Mahmoud et al., 2020; Shafee et al., 2020). Work-life balance is critical for the firm since it influences employee motivation, allowing them to continue to exhibit dedication to their jobs. Furthermore, it is necessary to strike a balance between work-life balance and job motivation (Shafee et al., 2020). Previous research has found a link between work-life balance and job motivation (Okotosatrio, 2018; Shafee et al., 2020; Sabir & Cura, 2021). The researcher then formulates the following hypothesis:

H1: Work-Life Balance will positively influence Work Motivation

Work motivation relates to an individual's psychological strength, which impacts how he behaves in an organisation, how persistent he is in solving difficulties, and how self-determined they are in their work (Tentama & Pranungsari, 2016). Motivation is a stage that analyses a person's direction and perseverance in reaching goals (Kocman & Weber, 2018). Motivational issues have become a critical issue in many organisations. Individuals who have a favourable attitude about work settings have a high degree of work motivation, whereas those who have a negative attitude toward them have a low level of work motivation and are unable to fill job openings. Work motivation, according to Maslow's theory, can be measured in terms of security, sociability, appreciation, and self-actualization (Rauan & Tewal, 2019). Work motivation is a human trait that has been shaped by external circumstances and has the ability to influence performance outcomes (Maulana et al., 2020). Motivating employees at work is critical because, with motivation, employees will be more enthusiastic about their work, resulting in better results (Said et al., 2020). Employees' abilities and knowledge will not be altered if they do not have a positive attitude and a positive, motivated attitude at work (Sidabutar et al., 2020). Workplace motivation is an endeavour to ensure that every employee performs well. Work motivation, it may be argued, is concerned with how employees can mobilise all of their potential and energies in order to work productively and accomplish good work results. Work motivation can underpin job pleasure when employees are genuinely enthusiastic about their jobs, and this enthusiasm can generate a sense of job fulfilment on its own (William, 2020). Previous research has found a link between work motivation and job satisfaction (Rozzaid et al., 2015; Maurya & Agarwal, 2018). Another study finds that work motivation has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction (Parimita et al., 2018; Sidabutar et al., 2020), implying that having excellent work motivation will boost our job happiness. The researcher then formulates the following hypothesis:

H2: Workplace motivation has a favourable impact on job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is defined as persons who are satisfied with their work at work. Job satisfaction is used to determine whether employees are optimistic or pessimistic about their jobs, which is why it is included in this study (Davis & Nestrom, 1985). Job satisfaction is subjective since everyone's level of satisfaction is different, and everyone's values are distinct (Muliana & Makmur, 2016). Employees that are happy with their jobs will be in better physical and mental health, which will have an indirect impact on the organisation. Job satisfaction is defined as a description of an individual's emotional response to a job, such that those who do a good job will feel satisfied (Obeidat et al., 2018). Job satisfaction can be defined as a positive or negative emotion based on an individual's assessment of their level of job satisfaction (Asbari et al., 2020). Work-life balance, according to McCutcheon (2014), is a serious problem and a critical concern for any working professional. The goal of a person's motivation is to

gather energetic energies that will encourage them to do new activities (Manivannan, 2019). As a result, more research into the function of motivation in boosting work satisfaction via WLB is required (Smith, 2010).

H3: Work-Life Balance will positively mediate by Work Motivation affects Job Satisfaction.

Figure 1. Research Framework

3. Work-life Balance and its consequences

Work-life balance has sparked a surge of interest in the subject of Human Resource Management study among persons concerned about the quality of their working lives and how they relate to their overall quality of life (Guest, 2002). The increasing diversity of family configurations in the workforce has increased the demand for work-life balance for a large percentage of employees (Parasuraman & Greenhaus, 2002; Greenhaus et al., 2003). Employees at a variety of companies have expressed dissatisfaction with the balance of their work and personal lives. According to a 2001 research conducted by Rutgers University and the University of Connecticut, 90 percent of working individuals claimed they do not have enough time to spend with their families (Lockwood, 2003). Employees are increasingly suffering from strain-based conflict, which occurs when stress associated to one position interferes with a person's capacity to perform another role, according to Korabik et al. (2003). Furthermore, there have been significant incidents of employees committing suicide as a result of their inability to combine work and life; following the suicide of a Japanese employee, Matsuri Takahashi, the Japanese government passed a bill in 2018 limiting overtime work (The Japan Times, 2018). When an employee fails to set aside adequate time for family matters, he or she experiences despair in the personal realm, which is carried over to work the next day, resulting in a lack of enthusiasm (Kumar & Janakiram, 2017). Since work-life balance has become a hot topic among employees, what are the factors that, if present, can help individuals strike a balance between their professional and personal lives? Because employees' perceptions of organisational support are one of the most important variables in promoting increased work-life balance among employees, organisations can play an active role here. They can aim to implement plans to improve their employees' work-life balance (Agarwal 2018; Thakur & Kumar, 2015; Kossek et al., 2011). Apart from addressing employee well-being, motivation, and satisfaction, businesses should strive to promote greater flexibility in the workplace, as work-life balance has numerous benefits for businesses, including reduced absenteeism and turnover, improved recruitment, increased productivity, and customer satisfaction, all of which have a positive impact on the bottom line (Clutterbuck, 2003; Mayberry, 2006; Morgan, 2009; Michie & Williams, 2003). Flextime, job sharing, telecommuting, parental leave compressed workweek, childcare, and eldercare facilities are some of the frequent work-life balance initiatives

that organisations may choose to use, according to some study (Beauregard, 2011; Fitzer, 1997; Bharathi et al., 2015; Pinsonneault & Boisvert, 2001). However, too much freedom makes it difficult for management to ensure that expected results and goals are met, therefore effective control measures are required to prevent workplace irregularities (Shagvaliyeva & Yazdanifard, 2014). According to Downes & Koekemoer (2011), several participants felt that colleagues' unavailability is a major issue since some employees abuse the flexibility provided to them. As a result, flextime should be introduced with caution only after establishing that personnel have acquired the necessary professional maturity to accomplish their jobs. Furthermore, the supportive nature of a supervisor and coworkers can influence an employee's attitude toward work (Chiaburu & Harrison, 2008; Michie, 2002), therefore managers at all levels must focus on enhancing internal connections.

3.1. The nature of public sector

The public sector is notorious for not only being rigid and reluctant to adapt but It's also known for its cheap pay. Its rigidity and unwillingness to adjust dates back to the inception of public sector organisations. The public sector's organisations were created with the intention of being impersonal and strong, with inflexible structures (Adair-Toteff, 2016). The organization's qualities include ensuring constant outputs through a strong and clear administrative chain, as well as having a lot of power (ibid). These traits are derived from Max Weber's (1864-1920) theory of bureaucracy. He believes that one's personal judgement should not be allowed to influence one's professional judgement (Haralambos et al., 2004). According to bureaucratic theory, an organisation should only run on the basis of justice and equality, and personal judgement and decisions that would eventually lead to nepotism and favouritism must be designed out of the organisation (ibid).

However, in order to achieve what the theory of bureaucracy was attempting to achieve, organisations must suffer severe repercussions. Bureaucracy requires organisations to be highly detailed in their structures in order to be impersonal and to limit any attempts to degrade professional functions and judgments. Every employee in the organisation has their own job descriptions, which must be followed in order to get a consistent result and minimise personal intervention. Unfortunately, because of this structure, the organisation has lost its ability to adapt and react swiftly to a changing environment, as well as its flexibility. It also prevents personnel from going above and beyond what they were hired to perform; each agency has its own job description and objectives (Dixit, 2002). The aforementioned repercussions are the result of maintaining its capacity as a public servant who must be able to maintain consistency in their outputs (Adair-Toteff, 2016). Stability is crucial for the public sector as a public servant because people rely heavily on it. Stability, on the other hand, places the public sector in a position where it is difficult to quickly respond to a dynamic and changing environment (Bosman, 2009).

3.2. The nature of motivation

The nature of motivation is divided into two categories: intrinsic and extrinsic motivation (Coetsee, 2002). Intrinsic motivation occurs when people enjoy doing something and the elements that motivate them to do so come from inside themselves. As a result, the motivational forces that drive an individual to act on something he or she considers essential, as well as the pleasure obtained from the output, stem from within the individual. The feelings of satisfaction, accomplishment, curiosity, and meaningfulness are among the driving aspects that motivate people from within (ibid). According to Coersee (2002), intrinsic incentives must be initiated by the individual. It is a type of self-rewarding behaviour that every employee engages in on a daily basis. Nonetheless, several studies have found an indirect relationship between motivation and employee commitment (Haque & Yamaoh, 2014; Haque & Aston, 2016; Faizan & Zehra, 2016).

3.3. Theory x and y of motivation

Douglas McGregor initially suggested the theory in 1960. The essential perceptions of this theory are employees' perspectives from the perspective of management. Theory X is founded on the notion that managers

have negative perceptions of their employees, such as avoiding work and responsibility, being unambitious, requiring punishment to attain organisational goals, being lazy, and not being particularly smart. Theory Y, on the other hand, takes a more optimistic view of employees. Employees are willing to take on new duties, love their work, are problem-solvers, are slightly ambitious, and want to contribute. According to McGregor (1960), managers' perceptions of their staff have a huge impact on their management style. As a result, understanding theories x and y will assist managers in selecting the management style that best suits the scenario. Contingency theory also aids managers in selecting management styles from theories x and y, or combining them, in order to obtain the best potential result.

3.4. Herzberg two factor theory

Herzberg's theory is based on a survey of 200 accountants and engineers who were asked about their positive and negative attitudes toward their jobs. According to Herzberg (1950), there are two primary characteristics that have a substantial impact on employee motivation and satisfaction. He refers to these two variables as motivational and hygienic factors, respectively. Being recognised, being able to enjoy one's work, and progressing in one's career are all motivating elements. Benefits, relationships, policies, and remuneration are all examples of hygiene factors. According to Herzberg (1950), the elements are disjointed and operate separately. While motivating variables have a direct impact on employee motivation and happiness, their absence does not necessarily result in employee dissatisfaction. Hygiene aspects, on the other hand, do not appear to improve motivation and contentment, but their absence will have a direct impact on employee unhappiness. Although motivating and hygiene variables appear to be unconnected and acting in isolation, according to Herzberg's two-factor theory, both motivating and hygiene elements must be managed fully and simultaneously to produce the best results.

3.5. Maslow's theory of needs.

People become motivated, according to Maslow (1943), when their basic needs are addressed. Maslow, on the other hand, proposes a hierarchy of needs, in which each stage corresponds to a set of demands, and people get motivated as the needs in each stage are met. The hierarchy begins with fundamental requirements like food, drink, and shelter and progresses to the pinnacle of what he refers to as self-actualization. To be able to sit in this plane of hierarchy, according to Maslow (1943), one must master the prior needs. The hierarchy of needs was expanded upon. Maslow's (1943) hierarchy theory emphasises and highlights factors that inspire people, particularly in the workplace. It does not, however, address the procedure. Maslow's theory of needs is based on two premises: people are motivated by a need for things they don't have, and once those items are attained, they cease to be motivating factors. Maslow proposed five characteristics that inspire humans in his theory of needs. It was questioned and critiqued, just like any other suggested or existing hypothesis. The final step of the hierarchy was one of the critics. The concept of self-actualization, according to Daniels (1982), is not fully evolved and is intertwined with self-transcendent. He then reacted in a follow-up study, expanding on the existing 5 to 8 characteristics that motivate people (Maslow, 1971). Cognitive, aesthetic, and transcendent needs are the other three aspects (Koltko-Rivera, 2006).

4. Theories of work life balance

4.1. The roots and terms

The term "work-life balance" was coined in the 1970s, according to Harrington (2007). Two important events are thought to have triggered the start of work-life balance. The first major event that triggered work-life balance concerns was the entry of women into the workforce. More skilled women are becoming significant assets to organisations, implying that businesses and organisations will soon have to satisfy the demands of female employees. Particularly when it comes to daycare, particularly for working mothers. The advent of EAP (Employee Assistance Programs) in the 1970s was the second major event (Harrington, 2007). Nonetheless, according to Zehra & Faizan (2016), females are less eager to work from home since they see it as a hardship.

Employee stress, illness, and despair, according to the EAP, have a major impact on productivity (ibid). Work and family became more important as the investigation progressed. These two big events do not necessarily indicate the beginning of the concept of work-life balance. Work-life balance, according to Redmond, Valiulis, and Drew (2006), has existed for a long time. Those two huge events, on the other hand, have brought work-life balance to the forefront and drawn attention to it. Many of the effects of work-life balance on organisations were later realised by companies. This realisation has a broader impact than only the private sector. Soon after, the public sector began to see the benefits of work-life balance for their enterprises.

5. Conclusion and implications for future research

Employee motivation has always been a critical part in an organization's performance, and work-life balance has piqued the curiosity of individuals concerned with the quality of their working lives and how they relate to other aspects of their lives (Guest, 2002). By looking into existing literature from a variety of secondary sources, this study attempted to connect these two critical characteristics for organisations from a theoretical standpoint. Several well-known classic and contemporary incentive theories have been applied, and they have been found to help firms implement work-life balance policies. In order to stay engaged at work, employers should show empathy to their employees and encourage them in striking a better balance between their professional and personal life, according to the research. However, managers must carefully consider the degree of flexibility provided and implement proper control mechanisms to ensure that a small number of employees do not abuse the benefits provided to them. The main effectiveness of flexible working practises is largely dependent on human resource practitioners' ability to address challenges and create a supportive organisational culture for employees in terms of work-life balance (Downes & Koekemoer, 2011). Because technology may sometimes make life difficult if not handled properly, staff must be instructed on how to be well organised before flexible working practises are used. This study was based on secondary sources; however, future research in this subject might be backed up by empirical evidence to show the requirement for work-life balance in relation to motivation theories by doing comparison analysis by gender or culture. By evaluating them in the context of these well-known theories of motivation, it may be possible to gain useful insights into whether or not work-life balance has the same impact on men and women or on employees across individualistic and collectivist cultures. As a result, firms may be better able to design work-life balance rules based on a deeper understanding of employee preferences and situational considerations.

6. References

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